

[microresearch]

Diamond Open Access

[awaiting peer review]

Triangulation of Compact Surfaces Using the Software Surface Evolver

Open Mathematics Collaboration*

December 11, 2024

Abstract

Considering that constructing and visualizing triangulations of compact surfaces in three-dimensional environments can be laborious and imprecise, we present a digital alternative. In this article, we provide a simple application of the Surface Evolver software, developed by Kenneth Brakke.

keywords: Surface Evolver, triangulation of compact surfaces, visualization

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14387348>

Introduction

1. This article is primarily based on the monograph entitled *Um Estudo Sobre a Triangulação de Superfícies Compactas* [1], as well as other references [2, 3].
2. Constructing the triangulation of a compact surface when embedded in a three-dimensional space can be a challenging and inefficient process using pen and paper. Thus, the use of software emerges as an interesting approach.

*All *authors* and their *affiliations* are listed at the end of this white paper.

3. *Surface Evolver* is software developed by Kenneth Allen Brakke that, through commands, allows the refinement of surfaces using triangulations, enabling their visualization in three-dimensional space.
4. The software is available at [4] along with tutorials and examples of various constructions.
5. Our goal is to present *Surface Evolver* and understand its relationship with the triangulation of compact surfaces, using it for refining a cube.

Preliminaries

6. This article is theoretically grounded in topology, a branch of mathematics that studies shape and space through continuity, focusing on properties of objects that remain invariant under continuous deformations, provided these do not involve tearing or crossing.
7. A classic example in topology is the transformation of a mug into a torus (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Topological transformation of a mug into a torus.

8. In topology, surfaces are two-dimensional manifolds. A surface S , having only two dimensions, is related to the plane \mathbb{R}^2 through homeomorphisms of the form $\varphi : U_1 \rightarrow U_2$, where $U_1 \subset S$ and $U_2 \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ are open sets. Thus, the local properties of S and \mathbb{R}^2 are the same. In this article, the surfaces under discussion are compact.

9. **Definition 1.** Let \mathcal{C} be a collection of subsets U_α of a topological space X , where $\alpha \in \Lambda$ (a countable set of indices).

If

$$\bigcup_{\alpha \in \Lambda} U_\alpha = X,$$

then \mathcal{C} is a *cover* of X . If each U_α is open, \mathcal{C} is called an *open cover* of X .

10. **Definition 2.** A topological space X is *compact* if every open cover \mathcal{C} of X contains a finite subcover that also covers X .

Triangulation

11. The triangulation of a surface can be understood as a mesh of triangles covering it or as a way of subdividing it.
12. In topology, a triangulation must satisfy a series of conditions to be valid, with compactness being a critical condition, as shown by Tibor Radó's theorem.
13. **Theorem 1 (Radó's Theorem, see [5]).** If S is a compact surface, then S admits a triangulation.
14. Based on this theorem, this work focuses exclusively on the triangulation of compact surfaces.

Triangulation of Compact Surfaces

15. Let S be a compact surface. A *curved triangle* on S is a closed subset $T \subset S$ together with a homeomorphism $h : T' \rightarrow T$, where T' is a planar triangle, i.e., a closed triangular region in the Euclidean plane \mathbb{R}^2 .
16. The homeomorphism $h : T' \rightarrow T$ maps the vertices and edges of the triangles as follows:
 - If v is a vertex of T' , then $h(v)$ is a vertex of T ;
 - If a is an edge of T' , then $h(a)$ is an edge of T .

17. Given two curved triangles T_i and T_j , where $i \neq j$, the intersection $T_i \cap T_j$ results in one of the following possibilities:
- i) $T_i \cap T_j = \emptyset$;
 - ii) $T_i \cap T_j$ is a vertex shared by both T_i e T_j ;
 - iii) $T_i \cap T_j$ is an edge shared by both T_i e T_j .
18. A *triangulation* of S is defined as a finite family of curved triangles $\{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_n\}$ such that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n T_i = S$.
19. If S admits a triangulation, S is said to be *triangulable*.

Surface Evolver

20. The *Surface Evolver* is a free software developed by Kenneth Allen Brakke, a professor in the Department of Mathematics at Susquehanna University, during his participation in the Geometry Supercomputing Project at the University of Minnesota.
21. *Surface Evolver* encompasses arbitrary topology, volume constraints, boundaries, prescribed angles, curvature, and more. It allows users to construct surfaces with polygonal faces via commands. The required data must be provided in advance by the user, who can also interact with the surfaces and modify their properties. Once the data is inputted, a visualization window enables direct manipulation of the surface.
22. The software uses triangulation to refine surfaces, progressively making them smoother as the number of triangles increases.

Triangulating a Sphere with Surface Evolver

23. We present an application of the software in which a cube is refined through triangulations until it approximates a sphere. It is important to note that after typing any command in the software, the user must press the “Enter” key to activate it.

24. To begin, prepare the code to be inserted into the program. The code for a cube, used in this example, can be found in [4].
25. Enter the code into a text file, preferably using the computer's notepad.
26. Save the file with the name "cube.fe" and open the program. The initial interface is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Surface Evolver Interface.

27. Type the name of the file in the program. In this case, type `cube.fe`.
28. In the "Enter command" field, type the letter `s` to open a new visualization window for the surface to be triangulated (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Generated cube.

29. Type `q` in the "Graphics command" field and then type `gogo` in the "Enter command" field. This will perform the first refinement of the cube (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Result of the `gogo` command.

30. In the visualization window, press `k` and move the figure. This allows us to verify that the surface has no interior points (Figure 5), consistent with the two-dimensional nature of surfaces.

Figure 5: The surface is hollow.

31. Now, press `e` to view the surface without a mesh (Figure 6). Despite this, the presence of triangles in its extension is still noticeable.

Figure 6: Surface without a mesh.

32. Use the `t` command to move the surface in the ambient space and `z` to zoom in, highlighting the polygonal faces of the surface (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Zoom on the surface.

33. Typing the `gogo` command again in the “Enter comand” field refines the surface further (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Result of the second refinement.

34. Removing the mesh reveals that the presence of triangles becomes almost imperceptible (Figure 9).

Figure 9: The surface becomes even smoother.

35. The `gogo` command can be used multiple times, depending on the computer's processing power. The more refinements applied, the closer the cube gets to a sphere, since they are homeomorphic.

Final Remarks

36. This article provided a brief contextualization of topology and the triangulation of compact surfaces, aiming to demonstrate the functionality of the *Surface Evolver* software through the use of triangulations.

37. Through the codes and commands of the *Surface Evolver*, it was possible to highlight the role of triangulation in refining a cube, bringing it closer to a sphere as the number of associated triangulations increases.

Open Invitation

*Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [6, 7].
Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Supplementary Files

[8]

How to Cite this White Paper

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14387348>

Acknowledgements

+ **Zenodo**

<https://zenodo.org>

+ **Surface Evolver**

<https://kenbrakke.com>

Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [7].

License

CC-By Attribution 4.0 International [9]

References

- [1] Corrêa, Guilherme Batista Fernandes. “Um Estudo sobre a Triangulação de Superfícies Compactas.” 2024.
- [2] Munkres, James Raymond. *Topology*. 2nd ed. Pearson, 2000.
- [3] Brakke, Kenneth Alan. *Surface Evolver Manual*. Pearson, 2013.
<https://kenbrakke.com/evolver/downloads/manual270.pdf>
- [4] Brakke, Kenneth Alan. *Surface Evolver*. 2013.
<https://kenbrakke.com/evolver/evolver.html>
- [5] Radó, Tibor. “Über den begriff der riemannschen fläche”. *Acta Litt. Sci. Szeged* 2. 101-121 (1925): 10.
- [6] Lobo, Matheus P. “Microarticles.” *OSF Preprints*, 28 Oct. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ejrct>
- [7] Lobo, Matheus P. “Simple Guidelines for Authors: Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics.” *OSF Preprints*, 15 Nov. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fk836>
- [8] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14387348>
- [9] CC. Creative Commons. *CC-By Attribution 4.0 International*.
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

The Open Mathematics Collaboration

Guilherme Batista Fernandes Corrêa¹

(lead author, guilherme.correa@ufnt.edu.br)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2489-5622>

Alvaro Julio Yucra Hanco¹

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6280-8775>

¹Federal University of Northern Tocantins (Brazil)